

ENGLISH FOR MANAGMENT DIRECTION STUDENTS TYPES OF SPEECH ACTIVITES IN TEACHING VOCABULARY

Murtazaeva Aisafar Bazarkulovna

Uzbekistan, Tashkent chemistry and technology institute

Department of: "Foreign languages" teacher

Tel: (90) 935-81-28. e-mail: aisafar81@mail.ru

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Annotation: in this article discusses Vocabulary teaching is the foundation of language teaching. Without perfect vocabulary, it is impossible to learn by teaching the types of speech activities. The interactive method of increasing the effectiveness of pedagogical activity (educational process) is showing its effectiveness in the study of English vocabulary for students of Management directions.

Key words: competitive, consequently, creative thinking skills, pedagogical activity, speech activities, vocabulary.

Izoh: ushbu maqolada so'zlashuvni o'rgatish - tilni o'rgatishning asosi. Nutq faoliyatining turlarini o'rgatish orqali mukammal so'z boyligisiz o'rganish mumkin emas. Pedagogik faoliyat (o'quv jarayoni) samaradorligini oshirishning interfaol usuli menejment yo'nalishlari talabalari uchun inglizcha lug'atni o'rganishda o'z samaradorligini ko'rsatmoqda.

Kalit so'zlar: raqobatbardosh, binobarin, ijodiy fikrlash qobiliyati, pedagogik faoliyat, nutq faoliyati, so'z boyligi.

Аннотация: в этой статье рассматривается словарный запас как основа обучения языку. Без идеального словарного запаса невозможно выучить, обучая видам речевой деятельности. Интерактивный метод повышения эффективности педагогической деятельности (учебного процесса) показывает свою эффективность при изучении лексики английского языка для студентов направления «Менеджмент».

Ключевые слова: соревновательная, следовательно, творческое мышление, педагогическая деятельность, речевая деятельность, словарный запас.

The modern demand in the world community for competitive personnel fluent in foreign languages is growing day by day. In the context of modernization of the country's economy, the social demand for competitive personnel with good knowledge of foreign languages, appropriate qualimetric and qualification characteristics is growing rapidly. Consequently, the formation of personnel fluent in foreign languages depends on the activity, personality, perception, attitude to their work, that is, personal and competent characteristics of foreign

language teachers who are able to professionally organize the educational process. Accordingly, the organization of professional pedagogical activity of foreign language teachers is one of the current pedagogical problems.

Extensive use of information and communication technologies, author's methods, interactive methods, new pedagogical technologies in the teaching of English, as well as enriching the teacher's work with various interactive tools, including interactive whiteboards, interactive audiovisual aids, e-textbooks and other advanced principles it is important to improve the educational content of the subject.

Vocabulary teaching is the foundation of language teaching. Without perfect vocabulary, it is impossible to learn by teaching the types of speech activities. It is used as material for types of speech activities. If the reader does not know the word, he will not understand the content of the speech, will not receive information. The content of the speech remains abstract to him. Because listening and recognizing vocabulary also has its own characteristics and difficulties.

The lexical side of speech has a peculiarity that the reader cannot speak if he does not know it. There is a special difficulty in reading, and students of Management direction must first understand letters and sounds, then read it, recognize words and be able to read them together, to understand their meaning. Only then can he understand and speak the content of the text. The lexical aspect of written speech must also be worked on separately, and the reader must be able to write, pronounce, and read a word in order to convey meaningful and accurate information through it.

It turns out that everyone needs vocabulary. For this reason, vocabulary is important in teaching Management direction students the types of speech activities.

Teaching lexical material is the goal and tool in teaching English pronunciation in a foreign language program. By methodical organization of lexical teaching we mean teaching the lexical side of speech activity, formation, teaching, automation of lexical skills.

Methodical organization of vocabulary includes:

- a) listening comprehension;
- b) to speak;
- c) reading;
- d) a written statement of opinion.

Teaching lexical aspects, skill formation are different from each other, they have a special feature. There are difficulties in the methodological organization, which must be taken into account.

They are:

1. Time spent teaching vocabulary;
2. By age of students;
3. For the purpose of training;
4. By stage of training;
5. On the skills of the student;
6. The abstract side of the word is one of the difficulties in expressing the exact meaning consists of.

Difficulties in learning words. Based on the relationship of English, mother tongue and Russian in the form, meaning and use of each word, the teacher should take into account the difficulties encountered in the process of teaching English vocabulary to students of Management direction and ways to overcome it. Then a specific method and ways to do this are selected. As a result, the specifics of each word are taken into account and communicated to students in a certain way. As a result, the reader learns to use the word quickly in speech.

We have been making extensive use of interactive methods, which are among the most effective methods available today in teaching English vocabulary in Management direction students. When choosing teaching methods in English lessons, it is advisable to choose based on the didactic function of each lesson.

(H. Rashidov, H. Khabib, G. Eldasheva, A. Zakirova Methods of teaching the block "Professional pedagogy". T.-2007. 60 p.) We know that the widespread use of interactive methods in the classroom leads to an increase in the level of mastery of English language materials. This requires a rational organization of the teaching process, constant stimulation of students' interest and activity by the teacher, the use of interactive methods to break down the content of the material into small pieces and encourage students to perform practical exercises independently.

(O. Tolipov, M. Usmonbaeva Application bases of pedagogical technologies. Science-2006.157 p.)

Interactive methods in special technique universities methods that activate students and encourage independent thinking. Interactive methods include:

- The method of "mental attack";
- The method of "severe attack of thoughts";
- "Cluster method";

- "black box" method;
- The method of "correct placement of images";
- The method of "working with red and green cards";
- "video puzzle" method;
- The method of "opposite attitude";
- The method of "work in small groups";
- "problem situation" method;
- "role-playing games", etc.

When the above methods are used, the student is at the center of the learning process, while the teacher encourages the student to actively participate. The benefits of the course for the student are as follows:

- decide on the interaction between teacher and students;
- Students have a thorough knowledge of the subject.
- develop students' independent, free and creative thinking skills
- Necessary conditions for students to realize their potential create conditions;
- the predominance of democratic and humanistic ideas in the pedagogical process must ensure the availability of
- study and learning with higher educational efficiency;
- high level of motivation of the student;
- taking into account previously acquired knowledge;
- Adaptation of reading intensity to the needs of the student;
- support for student initiative and responsibility
- study through practice;
- creation of conditions for bilateral views.

Conclusion. The interactive method of increasing the effectiveness of pedagogical activity educational process is showing its effectiveness in the study of English vocabulary for students of Management directions. Improving innovation and pedagogical activity in education is a set of scientific, technological, organizational, financial, commercial activities aimed at training competitive personnel, the purpose of which is to direct and provide the accumulated knowledge, skills, abilities, technology to socio-economic capital.

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